

Assessing ideal teacher's personality: Students' perspective and expectations

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ABSTRACT

The ideal teacher can reflect on self-development to form a personality that fits the needs of students. Teachers who have achieved a perfect personality figure have a greater chance of success in transferring knowledge and in the student education process. The need for an ideal teacher figure can be a reference for prospective teachers to develop themselves from the beginning of their education. Based on these needs, this study identified the ideal teacher figure based on the student's perspective. This research design used a survey research design in the quantitative method. The research subjects consisted of 240 students spread across the East Java, Indonesia. The data collection instrument used the student version of the teacher's personality test. Analysis of the research data was carried out in a statistical-descriptive. The results showed that the four strongest personalities most expected of students were caring, humble, responsible, and patience. Teachers' ideal personalities help them provide services that align with students' self-development needs. Suggestions for further research are identifying ideal teacher personalities based on other points of view, including senior teachers, student teacher candidates, and society in general.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Teachers are considered ideal figures in Indonesia. The Indonesian people towards teachers assume they act as role models. This assumption underlies the philosophical value of a teacher or *Guru* in Indonesian, which means *digugu* (their words are listened to by people because their words must be accounted for) and *ditiru* (their behaviour as are role models be imitated) [1], [2]. In other words, the teacher's personality is one of the main competencies that characterize an Indonesian teacher [3], [4]. The figure of a professional teacher in Indonesia refers to the educational ideology of Ki Hadjar Dewantara, the founding father of education in Indonesia. This ideology is embodied in the form of principles and mottos [5]: i) In the front as a model – an educator must set an example or be a role model or *ing ngarsa sung tuladha*; ii) In the middle to build spirit – an educator is always in the midst of his students and constantly builds their enthusiasm and ideas for work or *ing madya mbangun karsa*; and iii) In behind to support – an educator is continuously guides, supports, and points the right direction for the life and work of his students or *tut wuri handayani*. The figure of an ideal teacher in Indonesia should have this motto in themselves. They must dare to achieve change, become educators and motivators, show humility and wisdom, and create

a fun learning environment for students [6]. The motto needs to start with knowing and improving the teacher's personality.

These educational principles are expected to provide a learning climate that allows students to develop positive characteristics such as religiosity, sociality, gender, justice, democracy, honesty, integrity, independence, ability to fight, and responsibility [7]. So that the teacher's role is increasingly complex; namely, the teacher is not only an educator to achieve educational value but becomes an educator who develops positive character, morals, and positive culture [8]. According to Ki Hadjar Dewantara, teachers must be role models, role models as well as mentors for children/students in realizing characterful behaviour through the concept of *Tringa* (the three of *nga*, which is *ngerti*/know, *ngarsa*/feel, *nglakoni*/do) [9]. This concept refers to the teacher's responsibility to build good engagement with the students and the learning processes. In other words, a teacher's personalities have a significant role in supporting students' achievement [10], [11].

According to personality frameworks, the five personality traits [12] are a relatable framework for a teacher's role. The comprehensive dimension in the five personalities framework uses the biological, social, and cultural dimensions for personality differences [13]. The framework is supporting the teacher's role to involve and engage with the students and their academic environment, which have many factors and dimensions that influence each other. Furthermore, one of the dimensions to define Indonesian teachers' personalities is the national education standards statute on teacher's competence in Indonesia [14], [15].

Competencies that need to be owned by teachers include academic, social, personal and professional competence. Teachers who are skilled at teaching need to have a good personality and be able to make social adjustments (community adjustments) in the community environment. Personal competence is an individual ability that reflects a solid personality, is authoritative, becomes a role model for students, is responsible and has a noble character [16], [17]. The teacher's personality can change or shape the positive nature of students [18]. This change is by considering that students are imitators while teachers are considered ideal figures worthy of emulation to apply positive feelings [8], [19]. Therefore, the personality of a teacher is one of the determinants of successful learning [18], [20]. A role models with positive characters could impact the learning vibe and engagement, and it is presumed that the students will followed with the better vibe, spirit and motivation [21].

In contrast, several cases of excessive violence under the pretext of disciplining students are still an issue of education in Indonesia [22], [23]. On the other hand, several other issues also state that teachers are targets of student violence. Another phenomenon also mentions several violations of the law by teachers, both in the form of corruption, violence, sexual abuse, and other acts of violence [24]–[26]. These issues indicate these teachers' lack of fulfilment of the educator's code of ethics. This image can trigger the collapse of the Indonesian people's assumptions and beliefs that teachers are role models and role models for society [5]. Based on this, teacher personality indirectly related to burnout and other negative conditions [27]–[29].

Based on the ideas, the teacher's personality indirectly impacts the students, the learning environment and society. This impact will determine the student's academic outcome and, more comprehensively, their character, perceptions, belief, meaning of life and other nurturant effects [18], [30], [31]. So, a positive character teacher positively affects student character building regarding behavior, appearance, attitudes, and habits. In addition, the teacher's personality also provides social support and strengthens students' abilities [32]. In contrast, a teacher's lousy personality could also negatively impact the students' attitudes, behavior, appearance, and habit [25], [33].

This research on the teacher's ideal personality involved students' expectations and needs. Previous research has shown teacher competence in Indonesia is not fully optimized, and it is necessary to have teacher personality standards that can meet the needs and conditions of students. Therefore this study aims to reveal the ideal teacher from the student's point of view. The results of this study form the basis for factual standardization regarding the profile and perfect figure of a teacher from the student's point of view. The teacher's personality will support the performance and accuracy of the services the teacher provides to students.

1. RESEARCH METHOD

This research is cross-sectional survey research, a data collection method where information is obtained only at certain times but can be done for several days or weeks. Cross-sectional survey research is included in the descriptive analysis that aims to describe the conditions of certain variables [34], [35]. This study aimed to photograph the ideal teacher from the student's point of view.

The subjects in this study were 240 high-school students spread across the East Java, Indonesia. The 240 students are chosen using random cluster sampling to generalize the population with each cluster sample. There are 38 cities in East Java. Based on each city's population, school and area, this research clusters the

East Java area into two large clusters (the northern cluster with 18 cities and the southern cluster with 20 cities). Random selection was carried out in each group of 120 students. The samples are 26.67% male, and the rest are female. Their age is ranged from 15 to 18 years old. They are 63.33% from public schools, and the rest are private schools.

The instrument used in this study was a questionnaire developed based on the personality of the ideal teacher. The instrument is an assessment sheet of students' expectations and needs of teachers' ideal personalities. This instrument was developed based on the theoretical framework of the big five personality traits [13], [36], [37] which is integrated with Indonesian teacher competency standards [14], [15]. Furthermore, integrating the two frameworks produces 10 forms of Indonesian teacher personality. The 10 personality constructs are extraversion, social, agreeableness, behave, openness, smart, maturity, authority, self-evaluation, and conscientiousness. Based on the predetermined construct, the 10 sub-variables are defined more operationally as 27 personality items. The questionnaire is complemented by an answer construct with a score ranging from 0 to 9. The level of student expectations can interpret the predetermined score range according to the teacher's personality descriptor in the construct. More specifically, the content of the scores has the meaning unnecessary (score 0), not necessary (1-3), neutral/maybe necessary (4-6), quite important (7-8), and very important (9). This instrument has been tested for item validity and instrument reliability. The results of the item validity test through Pearson correlation showed that the lowest item score was 0.446, with a significant category at the 0.05 level. Furthermore, the instrument reliability test results showed a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.977, included in the high-reliability category.

Data analysis used in this study used descriptive and graphical analysis to determine the ideal personality from the student's point of view. The descriptive analysis will define the percentage of every personality item of the student's perspective and expectations. The graphical analysis will present the detail of the rating from the students.

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The data shows the degree of student perceptions related to their expectations of ideal teacher personalities. The 27 personalities are expected by the students, which means all of these personalities are good for teachers. However, there are some personalities which have a high degree of expectations from the students. The students' expectations level of teacher personalities is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Internal consistency reliability of biology test

Personality	Students' perspective	Expectation
Humorous	78.00%	Expected enough
Supportive	84.09%	Expected enough
Care	87.41%	Very expected
Be humble and not arrogant	86.06%	Very expected
Said softly	73.21%	Expected enough
Trained and skillful	74.85%	Expected enough
Communicative	78.26%	Expected enough
Have broad insight	82.74%	Expected enough
Diligent	76.09%	Expected enough
Responsive	79.02%	Expected enough
Creative and innovative	76.68%	Expected enough
Always smile	82.88%	Expected enough
Sensitive to problems	80.03%	Expected enough
Imaginative	76.80%	Expected enough
Have responsibility	87.02%	Very expected
Calm, not reckless	73.18%	Expected enough
Can control emotions	79.15%	Expected enough
Objective	70.70%	Expected enough
Can be trusted	82.44%	Expected enough
Must be authoritative	69.92%	Expected enough
Neat and clean	80.68%	Expected enough
Current or up-to-date	68.73%	Expected enough
Be patient	85.41%	Very expected
Inspirational	81.65%	Expected enough
Humorous	78.00%	Expected enough
Supportive	84.09%	Expected enough
Care	87.41%	Very expected

The data presented in Table 1 shows the distribution of personality data, the majority of which is expected as the personality of an ideal teacher. Furthermore, there is personality empathy in the form of

caring (87.41%), responsible (87.02%), humility (86.06%), and patience (85.41%) to be personalities that students highly expect. Furthermore, based on the data in Table 1, the graphical analysis reveals data on the distribution of student expectations for each of the four personalities. The results are presented in Figure 1.

The teacher's personality is part of the four competencies of a teacher. The teacher's main competencies are personality, academic, social, and professional competence, as required by Law Number 14 of 2015 concerning teachers and lecturers [14]. Many researchers consider personality competence (including personality patterns and styles) as one of the essential competencies of the teaching profession [8], [38]. Personality is one of the competencies that a teacher must own. The results of this study indicate some of the personality characteristics most expected by students in East Java. This fact follows personality competence, a personal ability that reflects a solid personality, is authoritative, sets an example for students, is responsible, and has a noble character [16]. The personality of a teacher according to the needs of students is one of the factors that influence the success of learning [39], [40].

Figure 1(a) shows the distribution of student expectation data on the "care" teacher personality. The data in Figure 1(a) shows that 67.92% of students have expectations of teachers to have caring personalities. Furthermore, no statements made teachers' caring personalities important enough for teachers to have. Figure 1(b) shows the data distribution on students' expectations of the "responsible" teacher's personality. The data in Figure 1(b) shows that 76.67% of students expect teachers to have a responsible personality. Furthermore, no statements that led to teachers' responsible personalities were not important enough for teachers. Figure 1(c) shows the distribution of student expectation data on the teacher's "humble" personality. The data in Figure 1(c) shows that 65.83% of students have expectations of the teacher to have a humble personality. Furthermore, no statements that led to teachers' humble personalities were not important enough for teachers. The data in Figure 1(d) shows the distribution of student expectation data on the "patience" teacher personality. The data in Figure 1(d) shows that 76.67% of students expect the teacher to have a patient personality. Furthermore, no statements led to teachers' patience personalities being not influential enough for teachers to have. The study of perceptions and expectations of teachers in this study describes four main student personality characteristics (caring, responsible teachers, humble and patient). These four personalities become personalities that students highly expect. At least, most students think it is essential for teachers to have these four personalities.

Figure 1. Students expectation of (a) care, (b) responsible, (c) humble, and (d) patience personality

The caring personality of a teacher refers to a sense of empathy that arises spontaneously through embracing, helping, and supporting with care. The results of previous research on caring personality competence need to be realized through three components (affective, cognitive, and behavior) [41]. A teacher's caring personality can provide social support to students' self-development. This support is provided by the social and emotional skills of the teacher [19] toward students.

Furthermore, responsible personality refers to the words and actions of the aware and earnest teacher, accompanied by a readiness to accept risks [20]. Responsibility must be part of the teacher's personality so that the teacher can carry out his primary duties professionally. The teacher's responsibility in the professional sphere leads to scientific/intellectual, professional, social, moral-spiritual, and personal responsibility [41]. The teacher's responsibility applies to the classroom's learning process and includes interactions with teacher students outside the school [32], [38]. Responsibility for teacher personality includes achieving student achievement and motivation and providing high-quality learning [42], [43]. So students' expectations about the attitude of responsibility need to be presented to fulfil the quality of education that can achieve goals.

A humble personality becomes the following essential expectation from the students. Humility refers to a person's ability to understand one's limitations, not be arrogant, acknowledge the weaknesses and strengths of oneself and others, and not be complacent. These humble attitudes can encourage student learning independence because teachers do not always feel self-righteous, do not blame easily, and tolerate student mistakes [44], [45]. In addition, a humble personality is also a reflection of teachers with good religious and moral behavior [41], [46]. A humble attitude also prevents teachers from students' misperceptions, which is essential in maintaining the emotional closeness between teachers and students.

The fourth personality in the sequence of teacher personality expectations by students is patience. The patience of a teacher tends to be seen through the ability to manage emotions with all stimulation from the environment. This personality relies heavily on the reflex response of a teacher to the stimulation and field conditions it faces. In some cases, a teacher's failure to respond can lead to excessive anger, violence, and even bullying of students [17], [47]. The teacher's patient attitude shows their maturity in social interaction [48]. The patient personality of a teacher tends to become character model for students.

The four personalities are personalities that show the identity of a teacher. Teachers need to have a consistent capacity for self-reflection to develop their personality [49]. A teacher's self-reflection process can bridge the internalization of values, attitudes, and awareness in forming the teacher's personality [50], [51]. The four teacher personality profiles based on the student's points of view need to be followed up as targets for the self-development of teachers in East Java. Achieving these targets needs to be accompanied by a capacity for self-reflection. Thus, the teacher can improve the quality of his learning service process [52].

On the other hand, a teacher's self-reflection is a critical component of the teacher as a reflective practitioner. A teacher's practical reflection contributes to the meaning of the process and success of learning to follow-up in improving the skills of learning outcomes [19], [53]. The reflective process leads to a form of self-reflection and self-practice. When the teacher has achieved an ideal personality and meets the needs of students, this personality indirectly provides reflection, helps, and serves students optimally [54], [55]. In the humanistic paradigm, the congruent and genuine personality of the teacher will unconsciously enter into the student's senses, and this situation becomes a reflection point for the teacher's personality to participate in and be imitated by students [30]. Furthermore, the teacher's ideal personality needed to support all conditions experienced by students as their social support [32], [56], and prevent them from having negative feelings [33]. In the end, a teacher's personality that matches student expectations can trigger a good emotional relationship between teacher and student. This good relationship will strengthen the involvement of teachers and students [10], so that the learning services provided can be more optimal.

3. CONCLUSION

The ideal teacher's personality considers students' expectations and needs. The four personalities that have significant urgency for students include care, responsible, humble, and patience. These four personalities contribute to building good relationships, providing responses and social support for students, and optimizing student learning outcomes. The ideal teacher's personality needs to be grown through professional self-reflection of the teacher. The results of this study have not explicitly examined students' perspectives on the personality of teachers with specific characteristics, both in terms of gender, culture, learning subjects, and schools. These limitations form the basis of what this research suggests the need for specific studies on students' perspectives on teachers with certain characteristics. These results also strengthen the practical implications for each teacher in the field in developing themselves and their professional personality.

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